

A quantomechanical explanation for the electronic transitions of the square-planar $[MLCl_2]$ complexes

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The present paper deals with the assignment of the absorption bands occurring in the electronic spectra of $[MLCl_2]$ complexes, where $M = Ni^{II}$, Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} and L is a new thioamide of the dibenzofuran series. EHT-MO calculations are performed for the free ligand and the complexes. Comparison of all the spectra shows that the nitrogen atom and the sulfur atom in the C=S bond are involved in the coordination.

Complexes of Ni^{II} , Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} with 3-(2'-thiothenoyl-amino)dibenzofuran (TTADBF) have been reported earlier¹. For all these complexes of general formula $[MLCl_2]$, where $L = TTADBF$ and $M = Ni^{II}$, Pd^{II} , Pt^{II} , an attempt to interpret the absorption bands occurring in electronic spectra has also been made¹.

The purpose of this paper is to give a quantomechanical interpretation of the absorption bands for the free organic ligand (TTADBF) and the complexes in order to get information about the heteroatoms involved in the coordination to the transition metal ions.

Results and Discussion

The electronic spectral data of the free ligand and $[Ni(TTADBF)Cl_2]$ are given in Table 1.

	16890	29585	34482	40000
TTADBF				
$[Ni^{II}(TTADBF)Cl_2]$	–	33112	40322	>40000
$[Pd^{II}(TTADBF)Cl_2]$	–	34780	39344	>40000
$[Pt^{II}(TTADBF)Cl_2]$	–	34482	39060	>40000

The free organic ligand (TTADBF) of structural formula,

has been modeled by means of HYPERCHEM 6. Its molecular geometry has been optimized using the Molecular Mechanics approach (MM^+).

The cartesian coordinates of the atoms corresponding to the bond lengths and angles thus obtained have been used to perform EHT calculations by means of ICONC program, an improved version of Hoffmann's ICON (QCMP116)³. The parameters (VSIP's and Slater exponents) used for calculations have been those recommended by ICONC library. The EHT calculations were performed without iteration upon charge and configuration. As far as the net charges on atoms in molecule are concerned, EHT exaggerates the electron transfer and, therefore, they cannot be considered as real.

Table 2 gives a sequence of MO energies and functions assumed as being involved in electronic transitions, the numbering being given by ICONC program.

No	MO energy eV	MO wave function	Occupation with electrons
41	-6 836	Ψ_{41}	–
42	-7 232	Ψ_{42}	–
44	-8 754	Ψ_{44}	–
45	-11 045	Ψ_{45} 1 p S_{32}	2
46	-11 399	Ψ_{46} 1 p S_{32}	2
48	-12 019	Ψ_{48} 1 p O_{20}	2
49	-12 192	Ψ_{49} 1 p S_{30}	2
50	-12 328	Ψ_{50} 1 p S_{30}	2

The MO's containing the most significant mixing coefficients are the following :

$$\Psi_{41} \approx -0.3533 O_{20}(z) - 0.2605 C_{16}(z) + 0.3499 C_{14}(z) - 0.2677 C_{13}(z) + 0.4273 C_{11}(z) + 0.3779 C_5(z) + 0.4060 C_2(z)$$

$$\Psi_{42} \approx -0.3142 C_{16}(z) + 0.3354 C_{14}(z) - 0.3163 C_{13}(z) + 0.3650 C_{11}(z) + 0.3510 C_6(z) - 0.4038 C_5(z) + 0.3798 C_3(z) - 0.3888 C_2(z)$$

$$\Psi_{44} \approx -0.4759 S_{32}(y) - 0.4210 S_{30}(y) + 0.3129 C_{26}(y) - 0.3499 C_{24}(y)$$

$$\Psi_{45} \approx -0.9194 S_{32}(x) + 0.2635 S_{32}(y) + 0.2318 S_{32}(z) + 0.1319 C_{23}(x) + 0.1885 C_{22}(y)$$

$$\Psi_{46} \approx -0.2207 S_{32}(x) + 0.5086 S_{32}(y) + 0.3469 S_{32}(z) - 0.4133 N_{21}(y) + 0.268 N_{21}(z) - 0.227 C_{14}(z) - 0.2407 C_{16}(z)$$

$$\Psi_{48} \approx -0.5787 O_{20}(z) + 0.3337 O_{20}(y) - 0.279 C_{14}(z) + 0.223 C_{12}(z) + 0.2285 C_6(z)$$

$$\Psi_{49} \approx -0.2802 S_{32}(y) - 0.4221 S_{30}(y) - 0.4375 C_{26}(y) + 0.4952 C_{24}(y)$$

$$\Psi_{50} \approx 0.7510 S_{30}(z) - 0.3191 S_{30}(x) - 0.203 C_{26}(z) - 0.2369 C_{23}(z),$$

where p_x, p_y, p_z orbitals are shortly denoted with x, y, z .

As may be seen, Ψ_{45}, Ψ_{46} and the corresponding eigenvalues are practically localized on S_{32} , Ψ_{45} being orientated toward the ring containing S_{30} (it contains mixing coefficients for carbon atoms of that ring) and Ψ_{46} toward N_{21} (mixing coefficients $-0.4133 p_y$ and $0.268 p_z$). The two MO's may be considered as describing the two lone-pairs of electrons of S_{32} . In the same way, Ψ_{48} describes the electron lone-pair of O_{20} and Ψ_{49}, Ψ_{50} the two lone-pairs of electrons for S_{30} .

Table 3 contains the calculated transitions and the absorption maxima occurring in the UV-visible spectrum of the free organic ligand.

EHT electronic transitions (cm^{-1})	Absorption maxima (cm^{-1})	
45 \rightarrow 44	18479	16890
49, 50 \rightarrow 44	27730; 28827	29585
46 \rightarrow 42, 41	33570; 36764	34482
48 \rightarrow 42, 41	38612; 41086	40000

As may be seen in Table 3, the most probable EHT electronic transitions are the following : 45 \rightarrow 44, which is the electron transfer from the lone-pair localized on S_{32} and orientated toward the ring containing S_{30} to an excited state localized on the atoms in that region of the molecule. The

transitions 49, 50 \rightarrow 44 involve an electron transfer from S_{30} lone-pair to the excited state described by Ψ_{44} . The transitions 46 \rightarrow 42, 41 describe the electron transfer from S_{32} lone-pair orientated toward N_{21} to excited states localized on the dibenzofuran part of the molecule. The transitions 48 \rightarrow 42, 41 describe the electron transfer from O_{20} lone-pair to excited states localized on the dibenzofuran group. As may be seen in Table 3, the calculated electronic transitions can favorably be compared with the spectral transitions.

The results presented here are for the Ni^{II} complex only, the others being similar. The molecular geometry for the complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{TTADBF})\text{Cl}_2]$ has been optimized using the Molecular Mechanics approach (MM^+ , HYPERCHEM 6). The cartesian coordinates of the atoms were used to perform EHT (ICONC) calculations without iteration upon charge and configuration. Instead of VSIP's recommended by Underwood *et al.*⁴ for Ni^{II} , the following data⁵ have been considered (eV) : $V_{4s} = -7.56$; $V_{4p} = -3.84$ and $V_{3d} = -10.04$. We preferred these VSIP's values because ICONC library recommends $V_{3d} = -13.49$ eV which is obviously lower than V_{2p} values for the heteroatoms involved in coordination and which leads to the absurd conclusion that the σ -bonding is metal \rightarrow ligand.

The EHT-MO energies for $[\text{Ni}(\text{TTADBF})\text{Cl}_2]$ involved in electronic transitions are summarized in Table 4, the numbering of the MO eigenvalues being given by ICONC program.

Table 4 gives those MO energies which would have a correspondence in the MO energies of the free TTADBF. The connection between MO levels has been done from the analysis of the mixing coefficients of the corresponding molecular orbitals.

No.	MO energies eV	Assignment	Occupation with electrons
45	-6.839	Ψ_{45}	-
46	-7.229	Ψ_{46}	-
49	-8.484	Ψ_{49}	-
54	-11.604	1.p. S_{32}	2
55	-11.865	1.p. S_{32}	2
58	-12.175	1.p. S_{30}	2
59	-12.373	1.p. S_{30}	2
60	-12.611	1.p. O_{20}	2

The most probable EHT electronic transitions are reported in Table 5.

Table 5. EHT electronic transitions for [Ni^{II}(TTADBF)Cl₂]

EHT electronic transitions (cm ⁻¹)	Absorption maxima (cm ⁻¹)
54 → 49	25165
58, 59 → 49	29771, 31368
55 → 45, 46	37393, 40539
60 → 45, 46	43411, 46556

As may be seen in Table 5, the absorption maximum at 33112 cm⁻¹ occurring in the electronic spectrum of the complex should be assigned to an electron transfer from the electron lone-pair localized on S₃₀. This transition occurs at 29585 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the uncoordinated organic ligand. The shift toward higher wavenumbers can be explained by the enhanced antibonding character of Ψ_{49} describing the excited states.

Indeed,

$\Psi_{49} \approx -0.2838 S_{30}(z) + 0.5240 S_{32}(z) - 0.3109 Ni(z^2) - 0.2370 Ni(xz) + 0.5771 Ni(yz)$ contains mixing coefficients of Ni *d*-orbitals and hence the pronounced antibonding character of this molecular state.

The absorption maximum at 40322 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to an electron transfer from the electron lone-pair localized on S₃₂. This transition occurs at 34482 cm⁻¹ in the electronic spectrum of the free organic ligand. The shift toward higher wavenumbers is mainly due to the lowering of the energy of the electron lone-pair of S₃₂ as a consequence of the coordination to the Ni^{II} ion (level 46 in Table 2 (-11.399 eV) compared with level 55 in Table 4 (-11.865 eV)). This is a proof of the TTADBF coordination to the metal ion through the electron lone-pair localized on sulfur ion having the lobe orientated toward N₂₁ atom. The other predicted transitions from the electron lone-pair of the oxygen to excited states localized on dibenzofuran group are be-

yond the measurement.

The electronic transitions occurring in the electronic spectra of Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes (Table 1) can be explained in the same way. Unfortunately, EHT-MO calculations for these complexes containing 4*d* and 5*d* transition metal ions are less reliable than for Ni(3*d*⁸) ion, at least as far as the quantitative aspect of the results is concerned. One may presume that the assignment of the absorption maxima occurring in the electronic spectra of these complexes is the same as for the Ni^{II} complex owing to the similarities observed with the shape and the shifts of the absorption bands of all [M^{II}(TTADBF)Cl₂] complexes herein considered.

By following the EHT procedure, after making the assignments for all the electronic transitions in the free organic ligand and also in the complex, one can compare their wavenumbers, together with the assignments we have made. It clearly shows that the oxygen atom in DBF is not involved in the coordination, while the sulfur in the C=S bond participates to it, together with the nitrogen atom.

Experimental

The synthesis of the organic ligand (TTADBF)² as well as the preparation of [M(TTADBF)Cl₂] complexes, where M = Ni^{II}, Pd^{II} and Pt^{II}, have been reported earlier¹. An Unicam UV-visible spectrophotometer was used.

References

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